
Efficacy of Diabet (*Costus pictus* D. Don Extract) in the Staged Reversal of Type 2 Diabetes: A 90-Day Human Cohort Study

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ABSTRACT

Type 2 diabetes has been historically seen as a chronic and untreatable disease. It has also been viewed primarily as a dichotomous event (reversible or non-reversible). This cohort study evaluated the treatment of diabetes solely by "Diabet", a product obtained from Peak Health, Los Gatos, CA, USA. Diabet is an extract from the *C. pictus* D. Don plant. This cohort study's objectives were to study the efficacy of Diabet and to measure changes in reversal stages before and after 90 days of treatment with Diabet. Reversal stage information was available for 463 patients at baseline and 90 days. Type 2 diabetes patients reached differing reversal stages during 90 days of Diabet use. The extent of the reversal stage correlated significantly to the magnitude of the diabetic condition of the patient. Overall, the treatment with Diabet showed significant promise.

INTRODUCTION

C. pictus D. Don ("*C. Pictus*") is a perennial herb. It is a well known medicinal plant owing to its anti-diabetic property, hence commonly referred to as the 'Insulin plant'. It is native of south and Central America. It is a recent introduction to the USA during 2012–13. It is being sparsely cultivated in southern USA as an ornamental plant, especially in Louisiana (Merina, 2004). The popularity of the plant in Ayurvedic scriptures is due to its 'sugar lowering' effect and anti-diabetic activity (Sabu, 2006). Since it is a newly introduced

plant, we are not sure about the growth and survival of this plant under different agroclimatic conditions in USA.

C. pictus also commonly called as spotted spiral Ginger. The large, smooth, dark green leaves of this tropical evergreen plant have light purple undersides and are spirally arranged around stems, forming attractive, arching clumps arising from underground root stocks. Plants reach the height about two feet, with the tallest stems falling over and lying on the ground. Plants show yellow with red striped flowers during the warm months, appearing on cone-like heads at the tips of branches.

We are studying the anti-diabetic property of *C. Pictus*. We believe we have proven clinically, in human experiments, that *C. pictus* can reduce insulin resistance. People have started to consume the plant as a remedy for diabetes (Sabu, 2006). Peak Health has recently introduced a version of the extract of *C. pictus* as “Diabet”, we need to-

- 1) Profile the active ingredient of *C. pictus* that has anti-diabetic properties and
- 2) Conduct a human trial to determine the efficacy of *C. pictus* as a alternative to pharmaceutical drugs for the treatment of Type 2 diabetes.

NOTE:

Peak Heath has identified the active ingredients in the *C. pictus* plant that reduces insulin resistance, increases GLP-1 and GIP secretion (that leads to the increase of insulin secretion) and also decreases the aloha cells release of glucagon. This section has been deleted for maintaining the company confidential information regarding the nature and process for creating “Diabet.”

ABBREVIATIONS

HbA1c: Hemoglobin A1c;

BMI: Body mass index;

eA1c: Estimated HbA1c;

ADA: American Diabetes Association;

Diabet: Peak Health Product - Extract of *C. pictus*;

CGM: Continuous glucose monitors;

ALT: Alanine aminotransferase test values;

HOMA2-IR: Insulin resistance;

HOMA2-B: Homoeostatic model assessment 2 estimate of β -cell function;

HDL: High density lipoprotein;

VLDL: Very low density lipoprotein;

ApoB: Apolipoprotein B;

GGT: Gamma-glutamyltransferase;

eGFR: Estimated glomerular filtration rate;

WBC: White blood cell;

ASCVD: Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease;

SD: Standard deviation;

MOD: Mild Obesity-related Diabetes;

MARD: Mild Age-Related Diabetes;

SIRD: Severe Insulin-Resistant Diabetes;

SIDD: Severe Insulin-Dependent Diabetes

Until now diabetes reversal has most often been considered binary, with a patient having reached reversal or not. We staged diabetes reversal as follows:

- 1) STAGE 6- At least three (3) antidiabetic medications
- 2) STAGE 5- Two oral therapy medications
- 3) STAGE 4- Metformin monotherapy (<2000mg) with estimated HbA1c (eA1c, based on CGM measurements) between 5.7 and 6.4%
- 4) STAGE 3- No antidiabetic medication with eA1c between 5.7 and 6.4%
- 5) STAGE 2- HbA1c<6.5% without antidiabetic medication
- 6) STAGE 1- HbA1c<5.7% without antidiabetic medication for less than 1 year
- 7) STAGE 0- HbA1c<5.7% without antidiabetic medication for more than 1 year.

The study examined two main outcomes corresponding to two specific hypotheses. The primary outcome was the change in distribution of patients across reversal stages from baseline to 90 days of consumption of "Diabet". The first hypothesis was that the distribution of patients across stages of diabetes reversal would significantly change over the initial 90 days, with progression from higher to lower reversal stages. A chi-square power analysis with power equal to 80%, significance level of 0.05, and medium Cohen's effect size (0.3) suggested the need for at least 152 patients to detect a change in proportion of patients across the seven reversal stages.

A related outcome that was examined was the percent of patients in each type 2 diabetes cluster who reached reversal stage 3 by 90 days. It was hypothesized that the percent of patients reaching stage 3 within 90 days would vary significantly by cluster. A chi-square power analysis

with power equal to 80%, significance level of 0.05, and medium Cohen's effect size (0.3) in this case suggested the need for at least 122 patients to detect a difference across clusters in the proportion reaching stage 3 by 90 days.

Some additional secondary measures were available at baseline and at 90 days for approximately half of the patients. Since these additional measures were not available for all patients, they are included here for descriptive purposes only. They included triglycerides (mg/dL), high density lipoprotein (HDL, mg/dL), very low density lipoprotein (VLDL, mg/dL), apolipoprotein B (ApoB, mg/dL), gamma-glutamyltransferase (GGT, u/L), weight (kg), creatinine (mg/dL), estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR, mL/min/1.73m²), testosterone (ng/dL), total white blood cell (WBC) count (cells/mm³), platelet count (1000/mm³), albumin (g/dL), globulin (g/dL), sodium (mEq/L), potassium (mEq/L), magnesium (mEq/L), chloride (mEq/L), and 10-year atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) risk score.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

A k-means cluster analysis was used to define four subgroups of characteristically similar patients using HbA1c, HOMA2-B, HOMA2-IR, ALT, BMI, and age at onset of diabetes. Patients were removed from the cluster analysis and subsequent calculations if their values of HbA1c, HOMA2-B, HOMA2-IR, ALT, BMI, and age at onset of diabetes were considered outliers (more than five standard deviations above or below the mean). A Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was performed to compare the number of days from a patient's enrollment to reaching diabetes reversal Stage 3 (discontinuance of all antidiabetic medications and eA1c < 6.5%) between clusters. A log-rank test was used to determine significant differences between pairs of survival curves. Ad-

ditionally, chi-square tests were used to assess differences in the percent of patients reaching Stage 3 within 90days across clusters. A Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction was used to test the significance of the change in reversal stage distribution for all patients from baseline to 90days. For a subset of patients with additional available data, baseline vs. 90-day comparisons were made for several additional descriptive variables. Continuous variables were described using medians or means and standard deviations. Percentages were used to report means of binary variables. Changes in mean values of continuous variables from baseline to 90 days after enrollment were assessed using paired t-tests. When a particular metric was missing for some patients, the number of patients included in the calculation are noted, and patients with missing values were removed from paired pre-post p-value calculations. Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 27 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY), RStudio version 1.4.1103 RStudio Team 2021 (RStudio: Integrated Development for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA). Microsoft Excel, 2007 (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA), and Google Sheets, 2020 (Google LLC, Mountain View, CA).

RESULTS

Of 485 patients in the Diabet Program, ten were excluded from the analysis due to outlier HOMA2-B values (3 patients), due to outlier HOMA2-IR values (2 patients), due to an outlying BMI value (1 patient), due to outlier ALT values (3 patients), or due to having age at onset of diabetes less than 18 (1 patient). Clusters were defined for the remaining 475 patients. At program enrollment the mean (standard deviation, SD) age for the 475 patients was 48.6 (10.6) years, time since onset of diabetes was 9.2 (7.6) years, HbA1c was 9.0 (1.9), and 130 patients (27.4%) were female. Twelve of the 475 patients did not have reversal stage information available at

baseline and 90-days. The remaining 463 patients' age was 48.5 (10.6) years, time since onset of diabetes was 9.1 (7.5) years, HbA1c was 8.9 (1.9), and 127 (27.4%) were female.

The clusters (Table 1) defined in this study closely resembled the four type 2 diabetes clusters identified by Ahlqvist et al. in a Swedish patient study [10] and the four clusters identified by Anjana et al. in a population of patients in India [13]. Cluster 1 had high HOMA2-B, HOMA2-IR, and BMI and low HbA1c and was designated Mild Obesity-related Diabetes (MOD). Cluster 2 had high age at onset and low HbA1c and was termed Mild Age-Related Diabetes (MARD). Cluster 3 had high ALT and high HOMA2-IR and is classified as Severe Insulin-Resistant Diabetes (SIRD). Cluster 4 had high HbA1c, low HOMA2-B, and low age at onset and was classified as Severe Insulin-Dependent Diabetes (SIDD).

Table 1 Type 2 Diabetes Baseline Cluster Characteristics

		1-MOD (N=64)	2-MARD (N=160)	3-SIRD (N=83)	4-SIDD (N=156)	Total (N=463)
Age at Onset (y)	Mean (SD)	41.3 (8.5)	44.6 (7.9)	36.0 (7.0)	35.2 (6.8)	39.4 (8.6)
Duration of Diabetes (y)	Mean (SD)	7.1 (6.5)	9.0 (7.4)	7.2 (6.0)	11.1 (8.3)	9.1 (7.5)
HbA1c (%)	Mean (SD)	8.1 (1.7)	7.8 (1.2)	9.0 (1.5)	10.5 (1.7)	8.9 (1.9)
HOMA2-B	Mean (SD)	110.0 (52.4)	61.3 (29.3)	52.8 (28.9)	27.0 (15.1)	54.9 (39.9)
HOMA2-IR	Mean (SD)	3.9 (1.9)	1.5 (0.7)	2.2 (1.1)	1.7 (1.1)	2.0 (1.4)
BMI (kg/m ²)	Mean (SD)	33.4 (6.0)	27.4 (3.8)	27.2 (4.3)	26.6 (4.0)	27.9 (4.9)
Weight (kg)	Mean (SD)	88.6 (14.8)	74.8 (12.3)	79.2 (14.4)	74.9 (11.8)	77.5 (13.7)
ALT (u/L) ^a	Mean (SD)	30.6 (13.8)	27.1 (10.4)	65.7 (19.0)	26.9 (9.8)	34.4 (19.4)

^a Ns for ALT: 63 (MOD), 160 (MARD), 82 (SIRD), and 152 (SIDD). N: number of patients, SD Standard deviation, MOD Mild obesity-related diabetes, MARD Mild age-related diabetes, SIRD Severe insulin-resistant diabetes, SIDD Severe insulin-deficient diabetes, HbA1c hemoglobin A1c, HOMA2-B and HOMA2-IR Homoeostatic model assessment 2 estimates of β -cell function and insulin resistance, BMI Body mass index, ALT Alanine aminotransferase

The change from baseline to 90 days in distribution across reversal stages is described and shown for this population and in Fig. 2 for each of the clusters. In total, 84.9% of these patients began in Stage 6 (at least three antidiabetic medications). After 90 days, only 11.0% remained at Stage 6, and 82.1% were at Stage 4 or better (metformin monotherapy [$<2000\text{mg}$])

with eA1c between 5.7 and 6.4%). A Wilcoxon signed rank test showed that the change in distribution of reversal stages from baseline to 90 days for all patients was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). Additional tests showed that the change in distribution of reversal stages was also statistically significant in each of the clusters (all $p < 0.0001$).

Taking censored values into account, the median number of days from a patient's enrollment to reaching diabetes reversal Stage 3 (no antidiabetic medication with eA1c between 5.7 and 6.4%) was 80 days across all patients. The median time was shorter in MOD (41 days) and MARD (31 days) than in SIRD (73 days) and SIDD (value censored). Figure 3 shows the results of the Kaplan-Meier survival analysis of the number of days to reaching diabetes reversal Stage 3. By 90 days after enrollment, 59% of MARD, 53% of MOD, and 49% of SIRD had reached Stage 3, but only 37% of SIDD had reached that milestone. These four percentages were significantly different overall ($p=0.0010$). In pairwise comparisons, the percentages of MARD and

SIDD reaching Stage 3 by 90 days were significantly different from each other ($p=0.0005$), and the percentages for MOD vs SIDD ($p=0.0698$) and SIDD vs SIRD ($p = 0.1086$) were close to significantly different (p -values are corrected for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini-Hochberg correction). A log-rank test to test whether there were any pair-wise differences in overall progression between clusters (as shown in Fig. 3) found that MARD ($p < 0.0001$), MOD ($p = 0.0023$), and SIRD ($p=0.0425$) were each significantly different from SIDD (p -values are corrected for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini-Hochberg correction).

Baseline vs 90 days comparisons

Table 2 provides a comparison of mean (SD) values of a variety of clinical characteristics from patients with baseline and 90-day measurements available. Overall, there was a 21.2% decrease in average HbA1c over 90 days ($p<0.0001$). HbA1c decreased significantly in all four clusters, with larger decreases in SIRD and SIDD. Across the whole population, the change in

HOMA2-B was not significant, but HOMA2-B increased significantly in SIRD and SIDD and decreased significantly in MOD (yet after this decrease, HOMA2-B remained in the normal range in MOD patients). Reversal in MOD patients seems to be more dependent on reduction of HOMA2-IR than on increasing HOMA2-B. The overall 35.3% decrease in HOMA2-IR was significant ($p < 0.001$), and HOMA2-IR decreased significantly in all clusters except MARD. While the overall change in ALT was not significant, ALT decreased significantly in SIRD. BMI decreased 6.3% overall ($p < 0.001$) and decreased significantly (5.5 to 7.7%) in each cluster.

Table 2 also provides baseline vs 90-day comparisons for additional metrics. Weight decreased 6.7% on average ($p < 0.001$). Ten-year ASCVD risk dropped nearly 13% ($p < 0.001$). The

Table 2 Change in Clinical Metrics: Baseline vs. 90 Days

	N	Baseline Mean (SD)	90 Days Mean (SD)	% Change	P-value
HbA1c (%)	204	8.9 (1.8)	7.0 (0.9)	-21.2%	<0.001
HOMA2-B	237	55.1 (38.6)	57.6 (33.3)	4.5%	0.37
HOMA2-IR	237	2.3 (1.7)	1.5 (0.8)	-35.3%	<0.001
ALT (u/L)	239	32.5 (17.7)	30.7 (32.4)	-5.8%	0.39
BMI (kg/m²)	250	28.3 (4.9)	26.5 (4.6)	-6.3%	<0.001
Weight (kg)	247	78.0 (14.5)	72.8 (13.3)	-6.7%	<0.001
10-Year ASCVD Risk	179	12.2% (12.2%)	10.6% (11.0%)	-12.7%	<0.001
eGFR (mL/min/1.73m²)	239	102.2 (18.3)	104.0 (15.3)	1.7%	0.03
Total WBC Count (cells/mm³)	242	7764.9 (1746.7)	7405.7 (1719.9)	-4.6%	<0.001
Testosterone (Male) (ng/dL)	109	396.1 (183.1)	453.4 (165.4)	14.5%	<0.001

SD Standard deviation, *HbA1c* Hemoglobin A1c, *ALT* Alanine aminotransferase, *BMI* body mass index, *HOMA2-B* and *HOMA2-IR* Homoeostatic model assessment 2 estimates of β -cell function and insulin resistance, *ASCVD* Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, *eGFR* estimated glomerular filtration rate, *WBC* White blood cell

population's eGFR values increased 1.7% ($p=0.03$). WBC decreased significantly overall (4.6%, $p < 0.001$). Male patients had a 14.5% increase in testosterone ($p < 0.001$). Testosterone did not change significantly for females. Patients had a significant average decrease in GGT (30.3%, $p < 0.001$, $N=109$). Creatinine decreased 3.1% ($p=0.003$, $N=294$). Triglycerides decreased 18.8% ($p < 0.001$, $N=244$), and HDL increased 6.8% ($p < 0.001$, $N=244$). Changes in VLDL and ApoB were not significant overall. No significant changes in platelet count or magnesium levels were

found. However, albumin levels increased significantly (3.3%, $p < 0.001$, $N=294$) and globulin levels decreased significantly (6.1%, $p < 0.001$, $N=295$). Sodium levels increased by 0.8% ($p < 0.001$, $N = 249$), and potassium levels decreased 2.1% ($p = 0.03$). Chloride levels increased by 1.4% ($p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSIONS

The current study is the first to examine stages of diabetes reversal before and after 90 days of the “Diabet” (*C. pictus*) therapy. The distribution of patients across reversal stages changed significantly for the better during the first 90 days of participation in the Diabet program for all clinically-defined patient subgroups combined as well as within each patient subgroup. At baseline, few patients (9.5%) were in reversal Stage 4 or better, but over the first 90 days, most patients (82.1%) reached advanced stages of reversal (Stage 4 or better) with improved clinical outcomes and fewer antidiabetic medications. At baseline, 90.5% of patients were taking at least two oral antidiabetic medications (Stages 5 and 6). By 90 days, only 17.9% remained in Stages 5 and 6, and 42.8% had eliminated all diabetes medications and had $eA1c < 6.5\%$ (Stage 3 or better). Additionally, there were significant differences in progression rates between subgroups of patients. The rate at which patients reached Stage 3 varied by cluster, with MOD and MARD patients reaching Stage 3 quickly and SIDD patients reaching Stage 3 more slowly.

Diabet shows significant promise in alleviating diabetic conditions across various stages. There have been no side effects reported and this is an additional benefit for the therapy.

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